

Occupational Risk Factors of Work Stress and Family life of on Site Workers Amidst Covid 19 Pandemic: Basis for Psychological Counseling and Intervention Program

Prof. Leilani R. Santos
MAEd Educational Psychology
Jose Rizal University
2023

ABSTRACT

This study is intended is to identify the occupational risk factors of work stress and family life of onsite workers amidst Covid -9 Pandemic. Work stress is linked between the employee and the employer since the employee's performance is impacted by his or her stress level, which in turn impacts the company's performance. The majority of respondents were between the ages of 18 and 25, and the majority of them were female. There is not a significant relationship between the respondents' degree of occupational stress and their profile. Regardless of the potential for enormous growth, onsite workers continue to suffer from a high level of whittling down caused by factors such as high levels of stress and a lack of opportunities for advancement. The examination of the study's findings allows the researcher to provide a few critical recommendations that the onsite workers in the Philippines should evaluate and adopt to lessen workplace stressors. Performance awards are linked to the appropriate amount of supervision and training. Both of these factors are required for positive job behavior and the smooth operation of an organization. Despite the fact that there were more variables that could be considered as indicators of onsite workers' workplace stressor based on external and internal factors, the present study was only able to work on three of them because the literature supported these factors more extensively.

Keywords:- Stress, Work Stress, Organizational Risk Factors, Quality life, Covid-19.

CHAPTER ONE

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

A. Introduction

Work life is a distinct profession with its own set of stresses, with on-site employees reporting significant levels of stress in their occupations (Tibayan, 2013). On-site workers labor in a physically and psychologically demanding setting, perceive stress differently than civilians, and characterize their stress in terms of combat-related situations (Guy, 2013). As part of on-site worker training and job assignments, both men and women are exposed to a wide range of stressor events. Furthermore, on-site workers may face stressors associated with being a woman in a traditionally and predominantly male work environment (Bray et al., 2010). Occupational accidents and illnesses cause human misery and loss today. Despite efforts to make advances, around two million employees die each year from work-related accidents and illnesses.

According to the Philippine government, 2.2 million Filipino workers in medium and large firms have access to appropriate occupational safety and health (OSH) protection and services. In other words, 17 of the 38.8 million workers in the country do not have adequate working conditions. OSH circumstances at micro-firms and the informal sector offer dangers and hazards, according to studies (International Labor Organization 2006). According to OSH (2006), workplace mental health management is crucial to worker health and includes assessment of workplace dangers such as work-related stress, exhaustion, and violence. Management of mental health hazards in the workplace that is effective leads in increased organizational productivity, corporate success, and enhanced employee health and well-being (WorkCover Queensland, 2017).

Many factors can aggravate the causes of workplace stress. People's obstacles at work make their jobs more intriguing and engaging. However, there are some challenges that can have a negative impact. Chronic mental tiredness is caused by long-term stress, according to Nekoranec and Kmosena (2015). It is a real issue, particularly among young people who do not have time to relax. It is common for managers to work more than 12 hours a day and frequently become workaholics (those who are entirely committed to their work), and whose work cycle is completely disturbed, with no rest. According to Cupe's (2003) study, stress is produced by overwork, which is a health and safety hazard in an organization. Overwork is defined as: excessive duty hours, unreasonable job demands, and a variety of job activities that drive workers to work overtime, a lack of recreation options, and pressure to speed up work, check performance, and have no alternative for employees on their off days.

Furthermore, the sources of workplace stress range from personal issues to work overload, the physical working environment, the work situation, and conflicts among colleagues and managers. Many employees suffer from stress, which may lead to uncertainty and serious impairments in health and performance. The major sources of stress are most frequently unmanageable, unpredictable, and unknown. There are also various resources accessible, such as personal awareness and coping techniques. For example, time management, assertiveness, and techniques to boost self-confidence, among other things. Management may also use certain resources to reduce employee stress by offering services and facilities such as health facilities at the workplace, quick and on-time access to therapists, and free time activities and entertainment. Stress is linked between the employee and the employer since the employee's performance is impacted by his or her stress level, which in turn impacts the company's production. As a result, stress management is critical for both. Time management, discussing sentiments, and leisure activities were shown to be the most effective stress management techniques (Nekzada & Takeste 2013).

B. Theoretical Framework

This study, which is based on NIOSH theory, begins with descriptions of several models of job stress that are currently of scientific interest, such as the job demands-job control model, the person-environment (P-E) fit model, and other theoretical approaches to workplace stress. These models have a common characteristic with all modern ideas of job stress: job stress is defined in terms of the interaction between the job and the individual. According to this viewpoint, workplace stress and the risk for illness occur when job demands differ from the worker's requirements, expectations, or capacities. This fundamental aspect is implied in Figure 1, which depicts the fundamental features of a stress model used by researchers at the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH). According to this concept, work-related psychosocial variables (referred to as stressors) cause psychological, behavioral, and physical reactions that may have an impact on health. Individual and environmental variables (referred to as stress moderators) do, however, intervene to modify the impact of occupational stresses on health and well-being, as depicted in figure 1. (For a more detailed discussion of the NIOSH stress model, see Hurrell and Murphy 1992.)

Leaving aside the conceptual similarities, there are significant theoretical discrepancies between these theories. For example, unlike the NIOSH and P-E fit models of job stress, which acknowledge a wide range of potential psychosocial risk factors in the workplace, the job demands-job control model focuses on a narrower range of psychosocial dimensions pertaining to psychological workload and the ability of workers to exercise control (referred to as decision latitude) over aspects of their jobs. Furthermore, the demand-control and NIOSH models differ from the P-E fit models in terms of the emphasis placed on the individual. The P-E fit model focuses on individuals' judgments of the balance between work qualities and personal characteristics. This emphasis on perceptions connects P-E fit theory to another variation of stress theory attributed to Lazarus (1966), in which individual differences in evaluation of psychosocial stressors and coping techniques become key in determining stress consequences. In contrast, while acknowledging the relevance of individual variations, the NIOSH stress model prioritizes environmental variables in influencing stress outcomes, as depicted in figure 1. In short, the model predicts that most stresses, regardless of conditions, will be dangerous to the majority of individuals most of the time. Other models of stress and job stress place a similar emphasis (Cooper and Marshall 1976; Kagan and Levi 1971; Matteson and Ivancevich 1987).

Fig. 1: Theoretical Framework

These distinctions have significant consequences for both directing job stress research and workplace intervention techniques. The NIOSH approach, for example, advocates for primary prevention of occupational stress by focusing first on psychosocial stressors in the workplace, which is congruent with a public health preventative strategy. Although the importance of host factors or resistance is recognized in a public health approach, the first line of defense in this approach is to eradicate or reduce exposure to environmental pathogens.

Figure 1 depicts the NIOSH stress model, which serves as an organizational framework for the remainder of this section. Short articles giving summaries of current information on workplace psychosocial stressors follow the talks of job stress models and on stress reducers. These subsections discuss stressors and stress modifiers that have received extensive attention in the literature, as well as areas of rising interest such as organizational environment and career stage. Each summary, prepared by notable professionals in the subject, includes a definition and a brief overview of important literature on the topic. Furthermore, each contributor has been asked to include information on measurement or assessment methods as well as prevention practices in order to maximize the utility of these summaries.

The chapter's concluding portion summarizes current understanding on a wide variety of possible health concerns associated with job stress, as well as the underlying processes behind these impacts. Traditional problems, such as psychiatric and cardiovascular illnesses, are discussed, as are developing issues, such as impaired immunological function and musculoskeletal disease.

In summary, recent years have seen extraordinary changes in the nature and expectations of work, as well as the rise of job stress as a serious occupational health risk. This study aims to increase awareness of the psychological dangers provided by the growing work environment in order to better protect workers' well-being.

C. Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will benefit the following stakeholders:

- **Management.** The study's findings will serve as a baseline and stepping stone in restructuring seminars and trainings required for their personnel, addressing the demands of hard times while developing on-site workers' skills that will make them productive. This will also assist them in generating resource materials that would enhance working conditions, so assuring the quality of work life. The study's findings may be used as a framework for determining how to enhance their working styles. This will also serve as an excellent tool for developing better policies for the various seminars and trainings tailored to their staff.
- **On-site personnel.** This study will assist members of the respondent organization in better understanding how workplace stresses may be controlled in the company in order to improve and preserve their mental health and well-being. It will also promote employee empowerment, which may result in improved job performance of on-site staff and fresh insights into mental health promotion. The respondent organization may utilize the study's results to build and execute an updated mental health program and policies that will help organizational members comprehend workplace pressures and their implications on safety, as well as individual health and well-being.
- **Health Care Providers.** The study's findings will give fresh information to health care practitioners regarding workplace pressures that might cause difficulties in the physical, mental, and emotional states of employees and clients, as well as successfully launch preventative steps to decrease accidents.
- **Communities.** Communities can guarantee that the environment is safe and that healthy living is constantly encouraged. Community leaders can also use the findings to examine health and environmental concerns and minimize stresses.
- **Teachers and students.** The study will aid students and teachers in their discussions by providing fresh ideas and concepts on occupational stress management and mental health advantages.
- **Researchers.** Other parties with an interest in the same issue, such as future researchers, may use this paper as a reference in their research endeavor.
- **Educational establishments.** The current study will assist educational institutions by introducing new notions of workplace stresses and mental health promotion that may be used in classroom discussions, instruction, and the design of health and academic programs and curricula.
- **Additions to the body of knowledge.** The study will add to the body of knowledge in the education sector, allowing students and academic community members to better comprehend occupational stressor theories, their impact, and consequences on mental health, ultimately increasing the rate of student learning and results.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

A. Local Literature

➤ *Stress at Work*

According to the most current report published by global consulting company Watson Wyatt Worldwide, work-related stress is the leading cause of people leaving a business. The consultancy firm advised HR administrators to investigate if the degree of stress that workers face at work is to blame for the high turnover rate. Watson Wyatt (2011) said in its Global Strategic Rewards Survey that stress is the leading cause of employee turnover. Regardless, organization administration has placed a low priority on reducing employee stress levels. Rachelle Arcebal, Watson Wyatt critical rewards rehearse pioneer, discovered that bosses frequently "disparage employee stress levels as drivers of turnover." She added that, while base pay remains the top drawer and maintenance driver among firms in the district, job stress on employees is typically dominant.

The findings were the result of a research in the Asia-Pacific region, in which 450 firms with a total of 8,000 employees participated in April and May of this year. The Philippines accounted for 12% of the 450 organizations. Regardless, the overall survey secured 1,389 organizations with 15 million employees in 37 nations. The overall research, which will be released soon, is an annual global assessment conducted by Watson Wyatt to discover how firms in various parts of the globe address concerns on the most excellent way to attract, retain, manage, and reward workers.

There is a widespread belief that leaders are more stressed than non-leaders. However, if leaders also have a strong sense of control—a psychological factor known to have powerful stress-relieving properties—then leadership should be associated with lower stress levels. Using distinct samples of genuine leaders, including on-site workers officers and government officials, we discovered that leaders had lower levels of the stress hormone cortisol and reported less anxiety than non-leaders.

Leaders' conduct and effects have long been thought to influence how their subordinates feel (Nielson, Borg, & Guzman, 2010).

➤ *Theoretical Explanations of Workplace Stress*

Workplace stress has received a great deal of study attention, so much so that theories have arisen to explain the link that exists between stress and the work environment. The person environment (P-E) fit theory, the framework of occupational stress, and the demand control support model are the three most prominent and widespread theories of occupational stress. If stress is described in an emotional framework, it appears to be quite complicated and difficult to define due to the lack of a pure and exact definition of emotions. Emotions are a person's subjective feelings and moods; they describe a complicated shift in an individual's physical and psychological circumstances that influences cognition and action. As a result, anxiety, despair, wrath, and shame are all symptoms of emotional stress. Anxiety is regarded as one of the most dangerous emotional variables, causing several incurable issues and abnormalities in a person's activities. Emotion has a strong influence on human conduct, making it difficult to make rational decisions or behave regularly. Scholars and psychologists classified emotional theories into three categories: physiological, neurological, and cognitive. The physiological theory of emotion relates to the body's signal or response. The term neurological refers to the brain's reaction to emotions. A cognitive theory is a hypothesis that addresses the roles of cognition or brain activities in the production of emotions. Mercado (2011).

Although families are widely regarded as the primary source of social support for service members following deployment (Badr et al., 2011), some researchers have argued that the affect, cognition, and behaviors of spouses, as well as the quality of service member-spouse relationships, can exacerbate the development of such problems in service members.

Stressful organizational cultures are distinguished by low involvement in decision-making, the use of punishment and negative feedback (rather than rewards and positive feedback), conflict avoidance or confrontation (rather than issue solutions), and non-supportive group and leader interactions. Stress may harm both the person and the company.

Physical working conditions, such as noise, insufficient lighting, low or high temperatures, less space for more employees, a poorly managed working environment, improper air circulation, a poor office building plan, exposure to dangerous machinery, and a lack of entertainment facilities, all contribute to stress. These stressors contribute to organizational stress (PAP, 2003). According to them, there are various organizational factors that cause stress, such as less authority, job demand conflict, less decision making power, lack of briefing, organizational changes, unfavorable behavior of seniors, less appreciation, repetitive and insignificant work, ambiguous job responsibility, low salary, fewer chances of promotion, job insecurity, more or less work, work burden or underutilization of skills, bad communication, new advancements, deadlines, and so on. Work-related stress can be caused by a variety of circumstances, including workload, bad working environment, working alone, job uncertainty, and others. Stress is a variable that varies from person to person. People's stress levels vary even under comparable conditions due to a variety of factors. The degree of job stress is determined by the degree of job demands and the individual's capacity to regulate these job demands or freedom to make decisions.

B. Foreign Literature

➤ *Overview of Stress*

Work-related stress can result in disease, injury, and decreased organizational performance from a variety of causes, both work and non-work. Employers cannot control their employees' personal life or the stresses they may experience there, but they do have a legal duty to limit their employees' exposure to work-related elements that may raise the risk of work-related stress.

The Work Health and Safety Act (2011) requires company operators to do everything reasonably possible to eliminate or reduce risk to worker health and safety. This obligation extends to safeguarding employees against the dangers of workplace pressures. Many academics have defined the term stress. Rumbold et al (2012) defined one of the definitions as a "continuous process that involves individuals transacting with their environments, making appraisals of the situations they find themselves in, and attempting to cope with any issues that may arise." Stress denotes a scenario in which a person is under pressure and lacks the ability to cope with it. Stress also suggests a direct negative reaction for both the individual and the organization, weakening the initial purpose of goal fulfillment. Besides affecting employees' health and well-being, stress has an impact on the organization's reputation and productivity. The negative effects of stress include job discontent and employees' reluctance to work. The company's disadvantages would include a decrease in productivity and turnover, as well as a lack in work quality.

Prediction of occupational stress. The goal of the OHS Act is for managers to do all possible to avoid injury from workplace stress. This should occur whenever a new technique or job is given. Furthermore, in addition to physical dangers, such as manual handling or ergonomics, mental dangers should be considered. Work requests are the easiest to recognize. Work request risk factors, for example, work tempo and task assortment, are more easily seen than more elusive bolster risk aspects, for example, respect and management culture. It may be difficult to discern how drivers, for example, difficult clients, are balanced favorably or adversely by assistance from managers and other employees. In any event, experienced, capable managers will understand how the work environment relates with the work association. The

suggested precautionary approach to stress risk management consists of four stages: Recognizing the sources of possible harm to worker health and well-being; Examining the possibility of staff injury on a regular basis Developing and implementing initiatives to: address workplace calculations that provide a danger of mental damage; reduce the impact of stress on employees via excellent administration; and advance staff health and prosperity. To ensure continuous change, screen and survey the use and efficacy of the mediations. Sharma and Gupta (2011).

➤ *Management of Workplace Stressors*

McFarlane and Bryant (2007) investigated post-traumatic stress disorder in work contexts and risk management. Post-traumatic stress disorder has sparked a lot of attention in the workplace due to questions of employer responsibility and compensation. The impact is visible while dealing with job injuries for on-site employees persons. The stress condition was shown to have a significant influence on the employer's liability for psychological injury in the job. Emergency services are provided to high-risk personnel who want effective processes and rules in the workplace. Organizations have the challenge of limiting employee injuries and lowering organizational costs through the appropriate deployment of preventative techniques. The study's findings indicate that businesses must anticipate potential exposures to traumatic situations that might influence the workforce, as well as ways for coping with workplace repercussions, notably the negative results of stress. There is a need for high-risk personnel screening, particularly after a traumatic event or cumulative risk exposure in emergency services. Early intervention necessitates rapid access to evidence-based treatments with few obstacles to care. Understanding the effects of distress, as well as bad health, poor performance, and confrontation with management, is critical. The study clearly demonstrates the relevance of awareness and understanding on the impact of traumatic experiences, necessitating foresight and appropriate management of such occurrences and cumulative exposures to traumatic disorders.

Kelloway and Day (2005) performed research on workplace construction. The study's goals were to define a healthy workplace, examine the costs of unhealthy labor and environments, and provide firms with a healthy workplace model. According to the study, an employee's job is both a cause of disease and a source of health protection and recovery. The company may pay social and economic expenses as a result of unhealthy workplaces. The study's paradigm for a healthy workplace improves productivity and profitability.

In the health care business, role stress is a major challenge (Lambert et al., 2004). The influence of occupational stressors and coping methods on worker health in Japan's health care business remains unknown. The study looked at the connections between workplace pressures, coping techniques, employee health, and demographic factors. The study's findings suggest that workplace stresses, stress-coping techniques, and demographic variables are the best predictors of employees' physical and mental health. Questionnaires were employed to collect data from the nurses who served as responders. Several significant correlations were discovered among the study's variables. According to the study's findings, the number of persons in the family and workload are the strongest indicators of physical health. The best indicators of mental health include the chance of leaving the current job, coping technique of escape-avoidance, and a lack of workplace support.

Long-term professional stress has been linked to a higher risk of burnout (Maslach et al., 2001). The JD-R model, on the other hand, may be used for workplace interventions targeted at avoiding or decreasing burnout. To minimize staff tiredness, certain work expectations could be lowered or changed, according to the findings. Furthermore, increasing job resources may increase employee engagement. Burnout therapies are most effective when they are tailored to the most significant job demands and job resources in unique working settings. Each of these occupation-specific treatments should contribute to a decrease in job demands and an increase in job resources, which can lead to a reduction in employee tiredness and disengagement, as well as improved satisfaction at work (Demerouti et al, 2001). Long-term professional stress has been linked to a higher risk of burnout (Maslach et al., 2001).

Health promotion is a public health method that demands widespread engagement. It may be defined as activities and advocacy to address the complete spectrum of potentially modifiable determinants of health, including measures that enable individuals to choose and sustain healthy lifestyles as well as those that produce healthy living situations and settings. We may enjoy our lives more fully when we are free of sadness, anxiety, excessive stress and worry, addictions, and other psychological issues. Peace of mind is a natural state that everyone may achieve (Rhode Island Psychological Association, 2016). Health can apply to both past and present conditions. It is frequently used to indicate the absence of sickness or infirmity, but it may also refer to a condition of fitness and capacity or a reservoir of personal resources that can be relied upon when needed. The impact of your ideas, feelings, and actions on your life is referred to as mental health. Positive self-image results from good mental health, which leads to meaningful interactions with friends and others. A positive mental health allows you to make better decisions and manage with life's obstacles at home, work, or school (American Psychological Association, 2016).

The onset of emotional problems varies with the severity of the damage (Hoge et al., 2007). Military troops who lose consciousness after being injured are at risk of developing posttraumatic stress disorder. According to meta-analytic research, trauma intensity is the most important factor of post-traumatic stress disorder (Brewen et al., 2000). According to research, those who enter conflict with poor mental health are more likely to develop post-traumatic stress disorder than those who have minimal precombat difficulties (Leard et al., 2009).

Employers who collaborate with employees may affect not just the health of their employees, but also the enterprise/organization as a whole, in terms of efficiency, productivity, and competitiveness. According to Burton (2010), in order to establish a workplace that protects, promotes, and supports workers' total physical, mental, and social well-being, an Enterprise/organization should consider addressing content in four "avenues of influence," depending on recognized requirements. The physical and mental working conditions Personal health resources at the workplace, as well as community involvement by Enterprise. Mechanical/machine hazards; electrical hazards; slips and falls from heights; ergonomic hazards such as repetitive motion, awkward posture, and excessive force; flying fragments that could injure an eye; or the risk of a work-related motor vehicle crash are all stressors that pose a threat to workers' physical safety. This is not always true. Non-physical or psychological dangers in the workplace can sometimes compromise physical safety. Psychological stresses can be linked to injuries either directly or indirectly. Employees who lack adequate influence over dangerous workplace circumstances lack the control required to mitigate dangers to life and limb. As a result, a lack of control might directly lead to an injury. Indirect impacts, on the other hand, can be just as hazardous. Personal Health Resources in the Workplace, on the other hand, include the supportive environment, health services, information, resources, opportunities, and flexibility that an enterprise provides workers to support or motivate their efforts to improve or maintain healthy personal lifestyle practices, as well as monitor and support their ongoing physical and mental health. The activities, expertise, and other resources that an enterprise engages in or provides to the social and physical community or communities in which it operates, and which affect the physical and mental health, safety, and well-being of workers and their families, are defined as enterprise community involvement. It encompasses actions, skills, and resources offered to both the immediate local environment and the larger global environment.

C. Local Studies

Coping reactions or strategies are the unique behavioral and psychological attempts that people use to master, tolerate, diminish, or limit stressful circumstances, as investigated by Cruz et al (2010). Coping techniques, on the other hand, are defined by Garcia (2012) as methods in which individuals choose to respond to stressful events. The effectiveness of coping mechanisms may play a significant influence in lowering stress and improving work performance. Individuals must have the essential coping techniques, which stem from either their mental training to maintain positive thinking or the organization itself, which assists stressed individuals in coping with the impacts of stress.

According to Amato and Zijlstra (2003), there is a direct link between bad work organization and poor health. Stress is seen as an undesirable reaction of persons who are subjected to extreme pressure. Stress is defined as an imbalance between an individual's capacities and resources and the demands placed on them.

Other than essential pay, the research found that organization reward programs, the quality of the work environment, rotational assignments, periodic cash incentives, justify builds, career development, and training are the reasons that employees are drawn into an organization and remain loyal to it. According to Laura Sejen, Watson Wyatt Global Director of Strategic Rewards, despite the global financial turbulence, employers discovered that they believe it is difficult to attract and retain basic skills and top-performing personnel. Unlike their American counterparts, Asia-Pacific firms choose alternative means to reducing their personnel in order to stay afloat during bad times. Sejen observed that Asia-Pacific firms preferred movements were to rebuild organization, solidify enlistment, and reduce rate of salary increment. In the meanwhile, American companies chose to lay off workers, reorganize their organizations, and cease enlisting. According to Sejen, Asia-Pacific firms learned that whenever the economy recovered, it would be more expensive for them to re-enroll and prepare people rather than maintain their staff.

The physical setting of a work place, according to Mercado et al (2014), is a means for management to show their attitude toward their staff. According to the findings of this study, the work environment structure is connected to the degree to which organizational members acquire sentiments of possession, and feelings of possession and ownership are associated with employee attitudes and actions toward the job and the organization. A competitive work environment, according to research, may alter and influence an individual's attitudes, actions, stress, and performance. Physical work environment features such as noise, lighting, and ventilation have traditionally been connected to job satisfaction in office employees and are thus implicated in the impacts of work-related stress on health.

Though the literature mostly points to occupational stress as a common problem in many organizations (Pretrus, 2010), most researchers' real quandary stems not only from accounting stress in various types of industries, but also from the applicability and use of the term "stress" depending on the organization.

According to the study, work-related psychological pressures can also contribute to cognitive health and mental problems. The association between the psychosocial environment and mental health concerns among blue-collar employees was investigated. Low future prospects, a lack of learning possibilities, and a lack of workplace control were discovered to be associated to the need for recovery from depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and recovery after work. Workplace psychological pressures can also lead to increased rates of memory, decision-making, focus, cognitive complaints, and psychiatric issues (Soriano et al., 2013). Studies also demonstrate a link between occupational psychosocial risks and psychological and physical health.

D. Foreign Studies

According to Soltanzadeh (2012), aspects such as association constitutionalism, social pertinence of work life, and social reconciliation were the greatest predictors of job satisfaction among workers. Ghalvandy, Fatahy, and Soltanzadeh (2012). In Iranian universities, formal work and job security have become stressful issues due to a number of factors, including the lengthy procedure of workforce enrollment, grants assignment, and expressed need. Workload and staff showing hours have also disrupted a few activities in different areas, for example, research and administration. Samie and Noor Shahi (2011). Many studies on employee job satisfaction have been conducted in various countries.

However, because the directed learning's about the quality of work life in Iran are limited, it is critical that more and extensive research be conducted in this area. It is especially important when the expansion of work-life quality and its relationship to job satisfaction is proposed. A research on "Occupational Stress, Performance, and Emotional Intelligence: A Critical Review" was done by Kazi, Shah, and Khan et al (2013). The study's findings indicated that businesses should actively examine the problem of work stress by

thoroughly knowing all of the Stress contributing variables through learning and awareness. Employees should be provided frequent training in this respect.

Training will help students build strong emotional skills, which will eventually help them, improve their performance and manage stress in a proactive manner. A research on "Job Stress, Performance, and Emotional Intelligence in Academia" was published by Yusoff, Khan, and Azam et al (2013). According to the findings of the study, there is a negative association between Job Stress and Performance, while a large positive relationship exists between Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance. The study's findings indicate that faculty members at Pakistan's Higher Education Institutions should focus not only on recognizing Job Stress sources, but also on attempting to manage their emotional competences through a supportive work environment. In this approach, people may address the issue of job stress while also improving their job performance job-related stresses include social, organizational, job design, and work management elements that impact the psychological and physical states of employees (Leka et al., 2008). Poor work-life balance, high emotional demands, long working hours, job instability, unstable work contracts, and work intensification are among the most significant rising psychological stressors (Brun and Milczarek, 2007). They serve as a general reference to various workplace risks such as exhaustion, aggression, harassment, and stress. Employees' productivity, negative behavioral consequences, and psychological harm are reduced when they are exposed to these workplace dangers (Schaufeli and Greenglass, 2001).

OHS Body of Knowledge (2012) presents a psychological framework of workplace risks such as working hours, injury, time pressure, illness, cognitive and emotional demands, violence, lack of job control, aggression, poorly defined work roles, lack of management and coworker support, insufficient recognition and reward, organizational injustice, and conflict. They are distinguished by their contact with the work design and work core, via which they may impact numerous elements of the workplace via employee behaviors, job demands, and organizational rules. They can have a negative impact on individuals' mental and physical health, as well as the organization's outcomes. Other negative consequences include a delay in recovering from job-related sickness or stress. Increased levels of worker stress can lead to decreased organizational performance as measured by a decrease in client satisfaction, an increase in staff turnover, a decrease in productivity and efficiency, an increase in job injuries and absenteeism, a decrease in the quality of relationships, and an increase in health care expenditures. Stansfield and Candy (2006) discovered the significance of psychological work environment on mental health. Significant demands, limited decision-making options, poor rewards, and significant effort are all risk factors for common mental diseases, strong psychological demands, little social support, effort-reward imbalance; work pressure, strong security, and limited choice flexibility are all risk factors for common mental diseases.

Stress is a perceived imbalance between an individual's ability to respond and demand in situations when failure to satisfy the demand has serious implications. It progresses from stressor to stress response and long-term repercussions. Although a certain amount of stress can lead to better performance and motivation, occupational stress, which can be caused by extreme exposure to work hazards, has negative health effects, specifically on mental health and well-being. In order to have a negative impact, the stressor must be intense. There is an ideal degree of stress for each given work in order for performance to be at its peak. Performance increases with mental and bodily stimulation, but only to a limit. Work-related stress may be caused by job expectations, and employees are capable of managing provided job demands are not excessive, given the appropriate degree of autonomy, and supported by colleagues and supervisors (Workplace Health and Safety Queensland, 2014). Employment expectations should not exceed a worker's ability to cope, even if employment gives employee incentive and the opportunity to learn new skills.

Changes in an employee's mental and physical condition as a result of responding to the employment environment represent a danger or challenge. Organizational environment, harassment, management bullying, tough relationships with coworkers and administrators, career development hurdles, hours worked, job ambiguity, role conflict, and a lack of autonomy are all factors that contribute to workplace stress

(Collign & Higgins, 2008). If the stresses persist, employees are at a high risk of developing psychological illnesses, which can lead to organizational dysfunction, increased absenteeism, and lower job productivity. Intervention tactics can be used to aid managers in dealing with employee workplace stress.

On-site worker stressors linked with combat exposure are regarded as key risk factors in on-site worker organizations for psychological damage of service members. The stress of recurrent on-site worker deployments contributes to severe behavioral health (Shannon et al. 2007). Hosek et al. (2006) discovered that deployment length increased with the rate of unfavorable stress responses. The study found that 11% to 18% of on-site employees exposed to battle experience had elevated stress and mental illnesses, compared to just 9% of those who had no combat experience. The study's findings are consistent with earlier research that demonstrates posttraumatic stress disorder is common in troops who have served more than four months in combat (Adler & Castro, 2001). According to Ozer et al. (2003), on-site staffs that do non-traditional combat activities are at a higher risk of developing emotional disorders (Ozer et al., 2003).

Physical stresses can directly influence the human body through exposure to toxic substances, as well as indirectly through psychological stress caused by employees' concerns about the health effects of being exposed to harmful substances at work (Stanyer, 2014). They can include things like stress, noise, vibration, poor lighting, radiation, chemical hazards, and metals. Concerns about physical risks might lead to stress and mental health issues (Canadian Environmental Law Association, 2011). Heat exposure has been associated to impaired cognitive performance owing to dehydration, which has a direct effect on the brain (Cian et al., 2000). Behavioral reactions to chemicals, according to Evans (2003), are the outcome of psychological stress related with personal health hazards. Employee illness and absenteeism are connected to the physical stressor of excessive noise. Fried (2002) discovered that greater levels of noise are associated with higher rates of illness absence. In the absence of proper remuneration, employees may develop health issues and be unable to cope with stress caused by high noise levels (Ose, 2004).

Physical pressures have a detrimental influence on employee health and can lead to higher rates of sick leave (Allebek & Mastekaasa, 2004). Physical stresses in the workplace have been thoroughly reported in several nations (Haukenes et al., 2011). Stansfeld and Matheson (2003) divide noise into environmental and occupational categories, taking into account the influence of noise on human health and its presence in all human activities. It is physical phenomena felt in the job and is regarded as one of the most common worker complaints. Although people can adapt to noise environments to a high degree, it causes fatigue and a decline in one's intellectual working capacity and physical occupations (Saremi & Rohmenr, 2008). Noise pollution has been shown in studies to have a major impact on staff productivity and performance (Kahya, 2007).

Work activities cause workers to feel physical and emotional stress. To reach sufficient or superior levels of job performance, employees' health and well-being must be maintained. Excessive workplace stress can lead to negative results such as accidents, job blunders, injuries, and deterioration in mental and physical health. A health program design can create a safe work environment, increase worker productivity, and improve employee health by designing equipment, furniture, facilities, tools, and job demands that are consistent with the characteristics and expectations of employees (Occupational Health, 2001).

➤ *Synthesis*

In the context of the COVID-19 response, health professionals may be exposed to occupational risks that put them at risk of sickness, injury, and even death. Occupational risks include COVID-19 infections, skin disorders and heat stress from prolonged PPE use, toxins from increased disinfectant use, psychological distress, chronic fatigue, and stigma, discrimination, physical and psychological violence, and harassment (World Health Organization, 2021). Healthcare professionals have shown amazing perseverance and professional devotion since the coronavirus 2019 (covid-19) outbreak began, despite their dread of being infected and infecting others.

Furthermore, any covid-19 breakout at work is hampered by a lack of physical distancing. As a result, employees in areas such as transportation and social care are more vulnerable to Covid-19, with healthcare personnel being the most vulnerable (Karlsson & Fraenkel, 2020). Lack of personal protective equipment, exposure to infected patients, job overload, inadequate infection management, and previous medical problems have all been implicated as risk factors for Covid-19 in health workers. In the context of Covid-19, health workers confront an unprecedented occupational risk of sickness and fatality. Long-term solutions to protect health workers from the pandemic must be developed quickly (Mhango et al., 2020). The revival of masking and social distance, as well as increased illness rates, is heightening emotions of isolation and concern, according to Smith 2021. Concerns about getting infected with the virus at work, as well as job security, are two of the most prevalent workplace anxieties that lead to mental health problems in employees across all industries.

Nonetheless, there are clear patterns in a variety of industries indicating an increasing risk of transmission. This occupational category is particularly prevalent in service and sales occupations, cleaning and domestic labor, education work, meat-processing work, hotel work, and transportation work. COVID-19 outbreaks are more likely to occur in workplaces with physical person-to-person contact, insufficient ventilation, communal dining areas, shared work accommodations, and travel (World Health Organization, 2021). The COVID-19 crisis has increased the risk factors commonly associated with poor mental health—financial insecurity, unemployment, and anxiety—while decreasing the protective factors—social attachment, employment and educational engagement, access to physical activity, daily routine, and access to health services.

This has resulted in a considerable increase in the population's mental health difficulties. The mental health of the jobless and those facing financial instability was poorer than that of the general population in all nations, a tendency that existed prior to the pandemic but appears to have worsened in certain circumstances (OECD, 2021). Despite the fact that they were able to spend more time with their families and had to spend time going to work, most individuals did not improve their work-life balance in the midst of an emergency scenario, according to studies done all around the world. Because they spent more time in webinars and meetings, most people perceived the COVID-19 emergency situation to be more stressful. They didn't communicate much with their coworkers. The separation between family time and professional time was so pronounced that they struggled to manage. Uncertainty about job and the future exacerbated the situation (Lonska et al., 2021). Approximately 30% of employees reported that their work and personal lives had deteriorated, while 10% reported improvements in work and 13% in personal life. Short-term employment was found to have a detrimental impact on work life, but work done from home had a favorable impact.

In terms of personal life, younger age, living alone, less leisure time, and increases in the amount of care obligations were all substantially related with reported negative impacts. Spending time working short-term and having higher leisure time, as well as taking on additional care obligations, were all connected with a reported favorable influence on one's private life as compared to living alone or with a family (Brauchli et al., 2021). Burnout happens when a person fails to recuperate effectively between stressful events. Employed parents experience more pressures and recover from them more quickly than nonparents. Employee parents specifically express the following stressors: a loss of work-life balance, more duties both at work and at home, and increased worry for workplace safety due to COVID-19 infection (Coe et al., 2021).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the discussion of the research design used, the respondents of the study, the research environment, the research instruments, the data-gathering procedures and the statistical treatment of data.

A. Research Design

The descriptive research design was adopted in this study. It was used to collect existing information and data about the respondent's stress and coping mechanisms in order to get a better picture of the respondent's quality of work life. According to Trochim (2014), "a key reason for doing descriptive research is to investigate and become more experienced with a particular phenomenon of the researcher's interest in order to deliver a detailed description." The study's principal approach is descriptive research. It is a technique for obtaining information on the current state of a problem or event in order to characterize "what exists" inside the variables or circumstances of the situation. Surveys and observation are the two most popular forms of descriptive research instruments (Key).

The researcher utilized their observations from their experiences as a pedestrian to provide a personal description of the solution to the study challenge. Furthermore, descriptive research is frequently used to generate information to explain problems that have not yet been clearly defined or whose true scope is unknown. It enables the researcher to become acquainted with the concepts of the subject under investigation in order to aid the creation of insights and ideas. The current study was an exploratory endeavor since it sought information on the subjects and activities. The researcher analyzed current literature to validate their results and generate early research suggestions.

B. Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

The respondents were Metro Manila-based on-site personnel. The study used purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling strategy that picks a sample based on demographic characteristics and study aims. Heterogeneous purposive sample was employed to get a varied variety of perspectives, opinions, and insights on the factors under consideration from online daters. The sample elements were chosen based on the researchers' perception that they may produce a representative sample through competent judgment, resulting in time and cost savings (Black, 2010).

C. Data-Gathering Procedures

The respondents were given a rundown of the study before the questionnaires were distributed to them in accordance with the instructions. The timetable for the interviews has been developed, established, and validated. It was specified that the responders had one day to hand in their questionnaires. Following the completion of the instrument's validation and the selection of the respondents for the study, the researcher obtained a permit for the administration of the questionnaire from the officer with the appropriate level of authority. Using a variety of statistical methods, the result was tallied, and then interpretations were drawn from them. This allows the researcher to arrive at an interpretation of the study using the information provided.

D. Data-Gathering Instrument

The following are the research instruments and techniques that were used in the study:

➤ *Questionnaire*

The researcher conceived up the method in order to address the many different aspects of the topic that were investigated in this study. In the main portion of the questionnaire, there are a series of questions that pertain to the problems that are outlined in the statement of the problem. Ten different versions of the preliminary draft of the first questionnaire were distributed to each of the subject organizations, and each

received twenty responses each. The pre-test was carried out so that the precision and readability of the instrument could be established. In order to exclude the possibility of any bias being introduced into the results, the respondents from the pre-test were singled out and removed from the final list of respondents. Before the final copies of the questionnaire were distributed for the actual survey, improvements and revisions were made to parts of the document that were ambiguous and unclear.

Table 6: Cronbach's Alpha for Each Factor of the Instrument

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of items
Workplace Stress Scale	.885	.890	18

In order to determine the degree to which each component of the instrument might be trusted, an item analysis was carried out. According to Blunch (2008), an internal consistency of between 0.7 and 0.9 is considered to be good. On this particular scale, every single factor received a very high dependability grade. 88.5 was the value for Cronbach's Alpha on the Workplace Stress Scale.

It is not quite clear how high an alpha value should be given a dataset that contains a specific number of elements; therefore this topic is still up for debate. It suggests basing the evaluation of the appropriateness of a measurement on the required degree of accuracy. If you want to draw a precise distinction between the amounts of joy that someone gets from writing, you will need a measure that is more dependable than if you only want to make a general contrast between the two. On the other hand, given that the value of this questionnaire's chi squared statistic is much more than 0.8, we may safely believe that it is trustworthy (Field, 2009).

The questionnaire was evaluated using a process known as pilot testing, in which a more limited version of the sample was employed than was originally intended. In this stage of the process of carrying out a survey, the questionnaire is given to a portion of the total sample population or, in cases where the survey is being conducted in a less formal manner; it is given to a sample chosen at random. The primary objective of carrying out a pilot study is to investigate the practicability of a method that is going to be used, at some point in the future, in a research that is much more extensive.

E. Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were utilized in the interpretation of the data to ensure validity and reliability of the study.

- **Mean:** It is a measure of raw data's central tendency. It was used to characterize the nature of the observations or replies gathered from each of the selected respondents on the effectiveness of workplace stressor management and the mental health of on-site working persons.
- **t-test:** This formula was used to determine the significant differences in the perceptions of the two sets of respondents on the effectiveness of the management of workplace stressors in the respondent organization, when grouped according to demographic profile
- **F-test (ANOVA or the One-Way analysis of Variance):** This was used in determining the significant differences among the three or more groups according to the grouping category.

F. Data Management Tool

It was determined that using computer software would be the most efficient way to do the required statistical computations. In order to accomplish this objective, Microsoft Excel was utilized for data administration, and SPSS will be utilized to aid analysis of the data. A suitable coding scheme was developed in order to facilitate the incorporation of the acquired information into the computer software program.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results and discussion of data gathered based on the questionnaires used in this study.

A. Demographic Profiles

Gender

50 responses

Fig. 2: Gender

Age

50 responses

Fig. 3: Age

B. The Workplace Stress Scale

Thinking about your current job, how often does each of the following statements describe how you feel?

50 responses

Fig. 4:

I feel that my job is negatively affecting my physical or emotional well-being.

50 responses

Fig. 5:

I have too much work to do an/or too many unreasonable deadlines.

50 responses

Fig. 6:

According to EU-OSHA (2014), a sizeable portion of workplaces in Europe are affected by the psychological hazards and stress that are associated with work, as well as the adverse effects these factors have on both health and business. Changes in worldwide socio-political conditions, for example, expanding globalization and the establishment of a free market, developments in data and correspondence innovation, new types of legally binding and working time systems, and in addition noteworthy statistical shifts are a portion of the noteworthy changes that have influenced workplaces in the course of the most recent quite a while and brought about new world-related wellbeing and health challenges. Other noteworthy changes that have influenced workplaces in the course of the most recent quite a while incorporate changes in noteworthy statistics. In a more comprehensive social context, working life is impacted by the general quickening of the pace of life as a whole. This contributes to an increase in the amount of work that has to be done, a constant time burden, the necessity to multitask, and the requirement to learn new things merely to keep up with business as usual (Rose, 2013).

I find it difficult to express my opinions or feelings about my job conditions to my superiors.

50 responses

Fig. 7:

An investigation titled "Occupational Stress, Performance, and Emotional Intelligence: A Critical Review" was carried out by Kazi, Shah, and Khan et al. (2013). The findings of the study indicated that the researchers should propose to the businesses that they should take the issue of work-related stress very seriously and make an effort to completely appreciate all of the elements that contribute to stress by way of education and awareness. In this light, it is important that workers get consistent training in the development of robust emotional competences, which will, in the long run, assist them in improving their performance and coping with stress in a proactive manner.

Although most of the published research points to occupational stress as a common problem in many organizations (Pretrus, 2010), the real dilemma that most researchers face is not only accounting stress in a variety of different types of industries but also the applicability and use of the term "stress" depending on the organization. This is because the definition of stress can vary greatly depending on the nature of the business.

I feel that job pressures interfere with my family or personal life.

50 responses

Fig. 8:

I have adequate control or input over my work duties.

50 responses

Fig. 9:

According to the findings of a study that was conducted by Misoska and her colleagues in 2014, the management of a company can convey their feelings about the employees working for them through the physical setting of the workplace. It was hypothesized in this study that the structure of the work environment is connected to the extent to which members of an organization acquire a sense of ownership of the organization, and that emotions of possession and ownership are, in turn, correlated with employee attitudes and actions in relation to the job and the company. According to the findings of certain studies, a competitive work environment is one of the factors that has the potential to effect and influence the attitudes, actions, levels of stress, and performance of an individual. Office employees' levels of job satisfaction have traditionally been linked to the physical aspects of the work environment, including noise, lighting, and ventilation. These elements are consequently implicated in the ways in which work-related stress may have an influence on a person's health.

I receive appropriate recognition or rewards for good performance.

50 responses

Fig. 10:

I am able to utilize my skills and talents to the fullest extent at work.

50 responses

Fig. 11:

The establishment of working circumstances that have the potential to improve the quality of an employee's work life in an organization for the purpose of achieving higher levels of performance and productivity is necessary in order to create an organizational environment that is suitable for the performance of human labor. To put it another way, the organizational environment must have the capability to meaningfully satisfy an employee's organizational as well as personal needs, as well as the capability to shape organizational values that better support and promote employees' health and well-being, job security, job satisfaction, competency development, and a balance between work and life outside of work.

The environment or atmosphere of the workplace can be improved via organizational stress management centers. This method is the most straightforward way that can be taken to reduce stress while at work. It covers the evidence that may be used to identify stressful aspects of work as well as a description of methods that can be used to reduce or eliminate the stressors that have been identified. This strategy has the advantage of directly confronting the most significant contributors to stress in the workplace, which enables it to provide the most favorable outcomes. Regardless of this, managers occasionally report feeling uneasy when confronted with this approach due to the fact that it can involve alterations to work schedules or generation timetables, as well as changes in the organizational structure. In addition to this, it is recommended that methods be developed within the context of a framework that allows for continuous development, rather than with the intention of achieving an emotive and continuously favorable result.

My work prevents me spending sufficient quality time with my family

50 responses

Fig. 12:

There is no time left at the end of the day to do the things I'd like at home (e.g., chores and leisure activities)

50 responses

Fig. 13:

With the help of this standpoint principle, the researcher had the belief that identifying the employee's performance and their quality work life through the satisfied salary or wages, more benefits such as dental/medical and others, employee's recognition and promotion would significantly play an important role in significantly improving and maximizing the employee's job performance and in effectively carrying out their duties, which consisted of providing or producing services to the interest of the company and to the public. The daily grind often comes with a healthy dose of anxiety and tension. In modern times, it has evolved into an integral component of our daily lives. Stress can be overcome by them, but we cannot escape its presence. There are times when stress may be beneficial. But because it takes place during our working hours, it will negatively impact our performance at the office. The findings of the study indicate that male and female workers alike are exposed to high levels of stress in their respective places of employment. There is a consensus among the majority of employees working onsite, regardless of age, that the stress of their jobs is negatively impacting their effectiveness at work. To alleviate the effects of the stress, both the employer and the employee are participating in stress management and coping activities. In addition to this, the researcher was provided with the chance to construct an intervention program for stress management, which may assist in improving the quality of work life experienced by sites employees.

My family misses out because of my work commitments

49 responses

Fig. 14:

My work has a negative impact on my family life

50 responses

Fig. 15:

Working often makes me irritable or short tempered at home

50 responses

Fig. 16:

Onsite workers who participate in team-building activities, such as coaching, relaxation training, skills in time management, and stress management training, can assist staff members in developing a greater resistance to the stress brought on by their work or in improving their ability to manage specific sources of stress. Employees participating in stress management programs learn about the origins and causes of stress, the negative consequences of stress on their health, and the personal skills necessary to reduce stress levels. This preparation has the potential to immediately lessen the negative consequences of stress, such as unease and the inability to get a good night's sleep, and it also has the advantages of being inexpensive and simple to put into practice. On the other hand, these techniques only partially address the organizational causes of stress connected to the workplace. In such role, they are less likely to achieve results that are realistic in advance, address the underlying sources of stress, or result in improvements in the performance of the company.

My work performance suffers because of my personal and family commitments

50 responses

Fig. 17:

Family related concerns or responsibilities often distract me at work

50 responses

Fig. 18:

A great number of experts have provided definitions of the term "stress." Fletcher offered one of the definitions of adaptation, which he described as a "continuous process that involves individuals transacting with their environments, making appraisals of the situations they find themselves in, and endeavoring to cope with any issues that may arise" (Rumbold et al, 2012).

If I did not have a family I'd be a better employee

50 responses

Fig. 19:

My family has a negative impact on my day to daywork duties

50 responses

Fig. 20:

It is difficult to concentrate at work because I am so exhausted by family responsibilities

50 responses

Fig. 21:

Work requests are the easiest to differentiate amongst one another. In comparison to the more elusive support risk factors, such as esteem and administration culture, work request risk variables, for example, speed of work and job assortment, are substantially less demanding to recognize. It may be comparably difficult to understand how drivers, such as difficult consumers, are favorably or adversely balanced by the assistance from heads. In any event, knowledgeable and capable managers will have an understanding of how the mood of the workplace links with the nature of the task. The four phases that make up the suggested cautious approach of dealing with risk administration of stress are as follows: Recognizing the sources from which possible harm might be done to the health and prosperity of staff members: Examining the potential for members of staff to sustain injuries on purpose Developing and putting into action initiatives to: address the workplace factors that pose a risk of mental damage; reduce the impact of stress on workers via effective management; and advance staff health and prosperity Screen and do research on how the mediations are being used, as well as evaluate how well they are working (Gupta and Sharma, 2011).

C. Level of Workplace Stress

Stressor	Onsite Workers	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
How often do each of the following statements represent how you feel about your current job?	3.57	Often
My employment appears to be impacting my physical or emotional well-being.	3.27	Often
I have an excessive amount of work to complete and/or a number of ridiculous deadlines.	3.30	Often
It is tough for me to share my thoughts or sentiments regarding my working circumstances to my superiors.	3.66	Often
I believe that professional demands interfere with my family and personal life.	3.44	Often
I have sufficient control or input over my job responsibilities.	3.65	Often
For good achievement, I earn suitable acknowledgment or prizes.	3.74	Often
At work, I am able to put my skills and talents to good use.	3.94	Often
My job hinders me from spending enough quality time with my family.	3.65	Often
There is no time left at the end of the day to complete the things I want to do at home (such as chores and recreational activities).	3.68	Often
My family suffers as a result of my professional responsibilities.	3.70	Often
My job has an adverse effect on my family life.	3.57	Often
Working frequently causes me to be angry or short-tempered at home.	3.69	Often
My professional performance decreases as a result of my personal and family obligations.	3.77	Often
Family issues or commitments frequently cause me to be distracted at work.	4.15	Very Often
I'd be a better employee if I didn't have a family.	3.69	Often
My family has an adverse effect on my day-to-day professional tasks.	4.15	Very Often
I find it difficult to concentrate at work since I am overwhelmed by family obligations.	3.69	Often
Over-all Mean	3.68	Often

This table depicts the workplace level of worksite employees. With a weighted mean of 3.68, it demonstrates that they frequently encountered occupational stress. Stress denotes a scenario in which a person is under pressure and lacks the ability to cope with it. Stress also suggests a direct negative reaction for both the individual and the organization, weakening the initial purpose of goal fulfillment. Besides affecting employees' health and well-being, stress has an impact on the organization's reputation and productivity. The negative effects of stress include job unhappiness and the army's unwillingness to work. The organization's disadvantages would include a decrease in productivity and turnover, as well as a lack in work quality.

D. Significant Relationship

Workplace Stress Scale	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Age	3.71	0.72	0.38	0.54	Accepted	Not Significant
	3.68	1.86				
Gender	3.89	0.57	0.66	0.42	Accepted	Not Significant
	3.70	0.72				
	3.61	0.73				

It indicates differences in respondents' assessments of the extent to which workplace stresses are managed in worksite employees. It demonstrates that the elements in both physical and psychological stresses have no meaningful relationship with one another. With this viewpoint principle, the researcher believed that identifying the employee's performance and quality of work life through satisfied salary or wages, additional benefits such as dental/medical and others, employee recognition and promotion would significantly play an important role in improving and maximizing their job performance and in effectively executing their duties, which were to give or produce services to the interest of the company and the public. In everyday life, stress is quite frequent. It has now become a part of our everyday lives. They can cope with stress, but we cannot escape it. Stress is not always terrible. However, if it happens at work, it will have an impact on our performance. According to the findings of the survey, both male and female employees are under stress at work. Regardless of age, the majority of armies agree that job stress is affecting their job performance. To deal with the stress, both the employer and the employee use stress coping mechanisms. Furthermore, this provided an opportunity for the researcher to create a stress management intervention program that could help improve the onsite workers' quality of life.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter shows the findings of the study and the possible solutions or recommendations by the researcher.

A. Summary

The majority of respondents were between the ages of 18 and 25, and the majority of them were female. There is not a significant relationship between the respondents' degree of occupational stress and their profile. Regardless of the potential for enormous growth, on-site workers continue to suffer from a high level of whittling down caused by factors such as high levels of stress and a lack of opportunities for advancement. The innovative approach of the industry is what makes the Onsite workers defense so frightening and inevitable. Work circumstances in the Onsite workers section are distinct from those seen in other mechanical shapes. The delegates' movement is totally restricted to their work region and the regular places set aside for diversion and replenishment.

Throughout the working hours, bosses are coordinated to keep an eye on dependability in taking permissible breaks, which are additionally followed frequently, through frameworks. Exciting tiring adds to the physical and mental strain of the workers, leading to an increase in stress and burnout under the electronically checked work and firmly bureaucratized work administration that is the foundation of the study that there is a level of workplace in working in Onsite workers. Despite this, the number of people employed in the Onsite workers segment is growing. The company's growth rate has reached 46%. At no other time in history have young workers run an entire industry almost entirely on their own; at no other time in history has an entire generation of young, office workers worked only at night, frequently far from their residential community families; and at no other time has any industry maneuvered such a diverse group of young people into a world of pretend, charm, and relative riches as Onsite workers has.

B. Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The examination of the study's findings allows the researcher to provide a few critical recommendations that the onsite workers in the Philippines should evaluate and adopt to lessen workplace stressors. Performance awards are linked to the appropriate amount of supervision and training. Both of these factors are required for positive job behavior and the smooth operation of an organization.

There are several techniques to increasing onsite worker engagement, and your strategy should be based on what is best for your organization's culture. Understanding the true reasons for the high prevalence of workplace stressor will better position you to protect the organization from the same fate. Employees who are well-paid and have personal and professional development opportunities will be valuable members of the workforce in the future.

Three fundamentals in employee workplace stressor are competitive wage and benefits, flexible schedule alternatives, and employee training. These are the Holy Grail of recruitment and workplace stress reduction, especially for onsite workers. Reducing workplace stressors is based on the whole work environment provided to worksite employees. On site workers flourish when their work environment encourages them to pursue their goals and aspirations. Your top workers share your vision and ideals about what they want to experience at work.

In everyday life, stress is quite frequent. It has now become a part of our everyday lives. They can cope with stress, but we cannot escape it. Stress is not always terrible. However, if it happens at work, it will have an impact on our performance. According to the findings of the survey, both male and female employees are under stress at work. Regardless of age, the majority of employees feel that workplace stress is impacting their job performance. To deal with the stress, both the employer and the employee use stress coping mechanisms. Coping tactics have a favorable influence on job efficiency. This indicated that sites workers' job productivity may be improved by implementing coping mechanisms. This can be done, for example, by deciding not to do certain activities that conflict with others, receiving moral support from a family member, attempting to change societal definitions of sex roles, work roles, or family roles, setting priorities in order of importance and then scheduling time around them, modifying attitude toward certain roles or activities in order to prefer quality over quantity, and rotating attention from one role to another to ha Organizations and people can both benefit from coordinating their efforts to create an atmosphere conducive to the adoption of coping methods.

C. Recommendations

Despite the fact that there were more variables that could be considered as indicators of onsite workers' workplace stressor based on external and internal factors, the present study was only able to work on three of them because the literature supported these factors more extensively. This must be mentioned when discussing the limitations of the current study. Working on the remaining elements that have been proposed might, however, definitely anticipate a higher consistency of the stressors that worksite employees experience in their place of employment.

Another restriction of the study was overcome by the participation of several research assistants, which was the challenge of collecting data from a big sample drawn from three separate organizations. On the other hand, there was a dearth of research about the determinants of workplace stressors mentioned under internal and external categories, as well as the connection between those aspects and demographic profiles. This was still another shortcoming.

In subsequent research, however, it is likely that working on all of the variables that are suggested as indicators of workplace stressors for onsite workers would add to the contributions made by the work; furthermore, it would unquestionably broaden the contributions made by the study if both onsite workers' and heads' perspectives were taken into consideration rather than concentrating solely on one group of onsite workers.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adhikari, Dev Raj and Gautam, Dhruva Kumar, (2010) "Labor legislations for improving quality of work life in Nepal", International Journal of Law and Management, Vol. 52 Iss: 1, pp.40 – 53
- [2.] Agrawal, R. 2001. Stress in life and at work. Response Books. London
- [3.] Aiswarya M, "A Study on Effectiveness of Recruitment Process in HCL Technologies-on-site workers Chennai" International Journal of Management (IJM), Volume 4, Issue 3, 2011, pp. 14 - 18, ISSN Print: 0976-6502, ISSN Online: 0976-6510.
- [4.] Allebeck, P., & Mastekaasa, A. (2004). "Causes of Sickness Absence: Research Approaches and Explanatory Models". Scandinavian Journal of Public Health,
- [5.] Vol. 32, (Issue: 63), pp. 36-43. doi: 10.1080/14034950410021835.
- [6.] Amato, A.D. and Zijlstra, F.R.H. (2003). "Occupational Stress: A Review of the Literature Relating to Mental Health". University of Surrey. <http://www.survey.ac.uk>.
- [7.] American Psychological Association (2016). "Change your Mind about Mental Health". Retrieved from: <http://www.apa.org/helpcenter/change.aspx>
- [8.] American Psychological Association (2017). "Coping with Stress at Work". Retrieved from: <http://www.apa.org/helpcenter/work-stress.aspx>
- [9.] Amin, Z. (2013), A study on the Quality of Work Life in Indonesian Public Service Organizations to predict the role of Career Development and Personal Factor, International Journal of Applied Psychology 2013, 3(3)..
- [10.] Ana and Pawar, (2013), quality work-life and job satisfaction of employees in VTPS International journal of management research and review, March, Volume 3/Issue 3/Article No-7/2547-2556
- [11.] Anwar Abdellah Mejbil, Mahmoud Khalid Almsafir, Rusinah Siron and Ahmad Salih Mheidi Alnaser, (2013) "The Drivers of Quality of Working Life (QWL): A Critical Review", Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences, Vol.7(10), pp.398-405
- [12.] Badr, H., Barkat, T.M. & Milbury, K. (2011). "Couples' Psychological Adaptation to Combat Wounds and Injuries". Risk and Resilience In U.S. Military Families. Pp. 213-234, New York, Springer.
- [13.] Behnam Talebi, B., M. Pakdel Bonab, G. Zemestani and N. Aghdami, (2012). "Investigating the Relationship between the Employee's Quality of Work Life (QWL) and Their Effectiveness in Banking". European Journal of Experimental Biology, Vol. 2(5): 1839-1842.
- [14.] Boschman, J. S., Molen, H. F., Sluiter, J. K., & Frings-Dresen, M. W. H. (2013).
- [15.] "Psychosocial Work Environment and Mental Health among Construction Workers". Applied Ergonomics, Vol. 44, (Issue: 5), pp. 748-755. doi:
- [16.] Brewin, C.R., Andrews, B., & Valentine, J.D. (2000). "Meta-Analysis of Risk Factors for Posttraumatic Stress Disorder in Trauma-exposed Adults". Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, Vol. 68, pp. 748-766.
- [17.] Buckman, J. E., Sundin, J., Greene, T., Fear, N. T., Dandeker, C., Greenberg, N., & Wessely, S. (2011). "The Impact of Deployment Length on the Health and Well-being of Military Personnel: A systematic Review of the Literature". Occupational and Environmental Medicine, Vol. 68, pp. 69–76.
- [18.] Brun, E. and Milczarek, M. (2007). "Expert Forecast on Emerging Psychosocial Risks Related to Occupational Safety and Health". European Agency for Safety and Health at Work.
- [19.] Burton J (2010). WHO Healthy Workplace Framework and Model: Background and Supporting Literature and practices. Retrieved from: http://www.who.int/occupational_health/healthy_workplace_framework.pdf
- [20.] Canadian Environmental Law Association. (2011). "Early Exposure to Environmental Hazards Chemicals/Pollution and Associations with Chronic Disease". Retrieved from <http://www.healthyenvironmentforkids.ca/sites/healthyenvironmentforkids.ca/files/EarlyExpandCDScopingReview-lowres.pdf>

- [22.] Canadian Union of Public Employees. (2003). Enough Workplace Stress: Organizing for Change.
- [23.] Chiu, R.K. and Fransesco, A.M. (2003) "Dispositional traits and turnover intentions: examining the mediating role of Job satisfaction and affective commitment". *International Journal of Manpower*, 24, pp 284-298. Dittrich, J.E.,
- [24.] Christian, M.S., Garza, A.S., & Slaughter, J.E., (2011). Work Engagement: A Quantitative Review And Test of Its Relations With Task And Contextual Performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 64, 89-136.
- [25.] Cian, C., Koulmann, N., Barraud, P. A., Raphel, C., Jimenez, C., & Melin, B. (2000). "Influences of Variations in Body Hydration on Cognitive Function: Effect of Hyperhydration, Heat Stress, and Exercise-Induced Dehydration". *Journal of Psychophysiology*, Vol. 14, (Issue: 1), p.29. doi: 10.1027//0269-8803.14.1.29.
- [26.] Cirjaliu B., Draghici A., Jitarel A. (2016)." A PROPOSAL APPROACH FOR STRESS MANAGEMENT. Retrieved from: <http://www.toknowpress.net/ISBN/978-961-6914-16-1/papers/ML16-095.pdf>.
- [27.] Collign, T.W. & Higgins, E.M. (2008). "Workplace Stress", *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, Vol. 21, Issue: 2, pp. 89-97, Etiology & Consequences, Taylor & Francis Group, Informa UK Ltd.
- [28.] Cotton and Hart. 2013. Occupational Wellbeing and Performance: A Review of Organisational Health Research. Australian Psychological Society. 10.1080/00050060310001707117
- [29.] Cox, T., Griffiths, A., Rial-González, E. (2000). Research on Work-related Stress. European Agency for Safety and Health at Work. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities. Retrieved from: <http://osha.europa.eu/en/publications/reports/203>
- [30.] Emadzadeh, M.K., Khorasani, M., & Nematizadeh, F., (2012). Assessing the quality of work life of primary school teachers in Isfahan city *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research In Business*, 3(9), 438-448.
- [31.] Erbes, C. R. (2011). "Couple Functioning and Post Traumatic Stress Disorder in Returning OIF Soldiers: Preliminary Findings from the Readiness and Resilience in National Guard Soldiers Project. Risk and Resilience in U.S. Military Families pp. 47-67, New York, Springer.
- [32.] Evans, G. W. (2003). "The Built Environment and Mental Health. *Journal of Urban Health*", Vol. 80, (Issue: 4), pp. 536-555. doi: 10.1093/jurban/jtg063.
- [33.] Ghimire U (2014). Perceived Stress and its Association with Psychological Working Conditions. Retrieved from: http://epublications.uef.fi/pub/urn_nbn_fi_uef-20141019/urn_nbn_fi_uef-20141019.pdf
- [34.] Latha and N. Panchanatham (2010). Call Center Employees: Is Work Life Stress a Challenge, *Sabaramuwa University Journal*, 9(1); December 2010, pp 1-9.
- [35.] Gupta, M., & Sharma, P., (2011). Factor Credentials Boosting Quality of Work Life of BSNL Employees In Jammu Region. *Sri Krishna International Research & Educational Consortium*, 2(1), 79-89.
- [36.] Harms, P.D., Krasikova, D.V., Vanhove, A.J., Herian, N.H., Lester P.B. (2013). "Stress and Emotional Well-Being in Military Organizations", Publications of Affiliated Faculty, Nebraska Public Policy Center, Paper 31, Volume 11, pp. 103-132; doi:10.1108/S1479-3555(2013)0000011008. University of Nebraska., Retrieved from: http://ppc.unl.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/Harms_Stress-and-emotional-well-being-in-on-site-workers-organizations_2013.pdf. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- [37.] Haukenes, I., Mykletun, A., Knudsen, A. K., Hansen, H. T., & Mæland, J. G. (2011). "Disability pension by occupational class-the impact of work-related factors: The Hordaland Health Study Cohort. *BMC Public Health*", Vol. 11,(Issue:1), p. 406. doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-11-406.
- [38.] Hema Gulati, Dr.Sunita, "Challenges For Hr Managers In Indian on-site workers Industry With Respect To Attrition" *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, Volume 2, Issue 1, 2011, pp. 14 - 18, ISSN Print: 0976-6502, ISSN Online: 0976-6510.
- [39.] K. S. Sathyanarayana, and Dr. K. Maran, "Job Stress of Employees" *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, Volume 2, Issue 2, 2011, pp. 93 - 102, ISSN Print: 0976-6502, ISSN Online: 0976-6510

- [40.] Lambert, V., Lambert, C. Ito, M. (2004). "Workplace Stressors, Ways of Coping and Demographic Characteristics as Predictors of Physical and Mental Health of Japanese Hospital Nurses", *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, Vol. 41, Issue: 1, pp. 85-97, ScienceDirect, Elsevier Ltd.
- [41.] Hosek, J., Kavanagh, J. & Miller, L. (2006). "How Deployments Affect Service Members". The Rand Corporation. Santa Monica, Ca: The Rand Corporation.
- [42.] Jeromem S., (2013), A Study on Quality of Work Life of Employees at Jeppiaar Cement Private Ltd: Perambalur, *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies.*, September, Volume 1, Issue 4,
- [43.] Kahya, E. (2007). "The Effects of Job Characteristics and Working Conditions on Job Performance". *Int J IndErgonom.*, Vol. 37, pp. 515–523. Doi: 10.1016/j.ergon.2007.02.006.
- [44.] Kelloway, K. & Day, A. (2005). "Building Healthy Workplaces: What We Know So Far", *APA PsycNet*, Vol. 37, issue: 4, pp. 223-235, American Psychological Association.
- [45.] Lambert, V., Lambert, C. Ito, M. (2004). "Workplace Stressors, Ways of Coping and Demographic Characteristics as Predictors of Physical and Mental Health of Japanese Hospital Nurses", *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, Vol. 41, Issue: 1, pp. 85-97, ScienceDirect, Elsevier Ltd.
- [46.] Leardmann, C., Smith, T., Smith, B., Wells, T., & Ryan, M. (2009). "Baseline Self Reported Functional Health and Vulnerability to Post-traumatic Stress Disorder After
- [47.] Combat Deployment: Prospective U.S. on-site workers Cohort Study. *British Medical Journal*, 338, b1273.
- [48.] Leka, G. & Cox, T (2008) PRIMA-EF Guidance on the European Framework for Psychosocial Risk Management: A Resource For Employers and Worker Representatives. *Protecting Workers' Health Series No. 9*. Retrieved from:
- [49.] http://www.who.int/occupational_health/publications/PRIMA-EF%20Guidance_9.pdf
- [50.] Limm, H., Gündel, H., Heinmüller, M., Marten-Mittag, B., Nater, U. M., Siegrist, J., & Angerer, P. (2011). Stress management interventions in the workplace improve stress reactivity: A randomised controlled trial. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 68(2), 113-126.
- [51.] Maslach et al., 2001 C. Maslach, W.B. Schaufeli, M.P. Leiter **Job burnout** *Annu. Rev. Psychol.*, 52 (2001), pp. 397-422.
- [52.] Matthews, G. (2001). Levels of transaction: A cognitive science framework for operator stress
- [53.] McFarlane, A. & Bryant, R. (2001). "Post Traumatic Stress Disorder in Occupational Settings: Anticipating and Managing the Risk", *Occupational Medicine*, Vol. 57, Issue: 6, pp. 404-410.
- [54.] M. Melchior, A. Caspi, B.J. Milne, A. Danese, R. Poulton, T.E. Moffitt Work stress precipitates depression and anxiety in young, working women and men *Psychol. Med. Lond.*, 37 (2007), p. 1119. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214782914000177#bbb0210>
- [55.] Nalini Bikkina (2010) "on-site workers Call Centres: Psychosocial Issues and Related Ethical Conundrums" *Turkish Journal of Business Ethics* Vol. 3 Issue 5, p7
- [56.] Nekoranec, J., & Kmosena, M. (2015). Stress in the workplace - sources, effects and coping strategies. *Review of the Air Force Academy*(1), 163-170.
- [57.] Nekzada N. & Tekeste F.(2013). 'Stress Causes and its Management at the Workplace'. Retrieved from: <https://www.coursehero.com/file/23103310/stress/>.
- [58.] Noor, S.M., & Abdullah, M.A., (2012). Quality Work Life among Factory Workers in Malaysia. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 35, 739-745.
- [59.] Normala, Daud (2010). "Investigating the Relationship between Quality of Work Life and Organizational Commitment amongst Employees in Malaysian Firms". *Faculty of Business Management in University of Technology, MARA, international journal of business and management*, 5(10)
- [60.] Occupational Health (2001). "Occupational Ergonomics", *Manual for Primary Health Care Workers*, pp. 82-84, Doc: WHO-EM/OCH/085/E/L04.01/2000. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Retrieved From: <http://www.who.int>.

- [61.] OHS Body of Knowledge (2012). "Psychosocial Hazards and Occupational Stress". Health and Safety Professionals Alliance. Pp. 1-35, Safety Institute of Australia, Ltd. ISBN: 978-0-9808743-1-0. Retrieved From: <http://www.ohsbok.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2013/12/19-Hazard-Psychosocial.pdf?ce18fc>
- [62.] Ozer, E.J., Best, S.R., Lipsey, T.L., & Weiss, D.S. (2003). "Predictors of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Symptoms in Adults: A Meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, Vol. 129(Issue: 1), pp. 52-73.
- [63.] Rhode Island Psychological Association (2016) "Useful Psychology Information: Importance of Mental Health". Retrieved from:<http://www.ripsych.org/importance-of-mental-health>
- [64.] Rondinone, B. M., Persechino, B., Castaldi, T., Valenti, A., Ferrante, P., Ronchetti, M., & Iavicoli, S. (2012). Work-related stress risk assessment in Italy: the validation study of health safety and executive indicator tool. *G Ital Med Lav Erg*, 34(4), 392-9
- [65.] Schaufeli, W.B. Greenglass E.R. (2001). "Introduction to Special Issue on Burnout and Health". *Psychology and Health*, Vol. 16, pp. 501-510.
- [66.] Stenfors, C. D., Magnusson H, L., Oxenstierna, G., Theorell, T., & Nilsson, L. (2013). "Psychosocial Working Conditions and Cognitive Complaints Among Swedish Employees", *Plos ONE*, Vol. 8, (Issue: 4), pp. 1-10. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0060637.
- [68.] Saremi, M., Rohmer, O., (2008). "Combined Effects of Noise and Shift Work on Fatigue as a Function of Age. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*. Vol.14. pp. 387–394.
- [69.] Shannon, S.D., Hoffman, J.S., James, L.C., Johnson, J.E., Magee, T.N., and Riggs, D. (2007). "American Psychological Association's Presidential Task Force on Military Deployment Services for Youth, Families, and Service Members", *Military Deployment Services TF Report*.
- [70.] Stansfeld S.A., Matheson M.P. (2003). "Noise Pollution: Non-auditory Effects on Health". *Brit Med Bull*. Vol. 68, pp. 243–257. doi: 10.1093/bmb/ldg033.
- [71.] Stanyer, K.R. (2014). "Impact of Physical and Psychosocial Workplace Hazards on Employee Health: An Irish Tale of Civil Servants Workers", Dissertation Paper 1401, Clemson University, TigerPrints. Retrieved from: <http://tigerprints.clemson.edu>.
- [72.] Tabassum, A., Rahman, T., & Jahan, K., (2011). A Comparative Analysis of Quality of Work Life among the Employees of Local Private and Foreign Commercial Banks in Bangladesh. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 17 33.
- [73.] Tennant, C. (2001). Work-related Stress and Depressive Disorders. *Journal of Psychosomatic research*, 51 (3) 697-704.
- [74.] Vasterling, J.J., Proctor, S.D., Friedman, M.J., Hoge, C.W., Heeren, T., King, L.A., King, D.W. (2010). "PTSD Symptom Increases in Iraq-deployed Soldiers: Comparison with Non-deployed Soldiers and Associations with Baseline Symptoms, Deployed Experiences, and Post-deployment Stress", *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, Vol. 23, Issue:1, pp. 41-51, The International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies. John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- [75.] Workplace Health and Safety Queensland (2014). "Overview of Work-related Stress". P. 9, Department of Justice & Attorney General. Retrieved from: <http://www.worksafe.qld.gov.au>.

CURRICULUM VITAE

LEILANI REVENTAR SANTOS

Mandaluyong City
0993-4859782
lheisaints@gmail.com
<http://ph.linkedin.com/in/leighsaints>

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Psychology
New Era University (2003-2006)

Bachelor in Science Major in Psychology, New Era University (1998-2002)
New Era University, Secondary (1994-1998)
Jose Rizal University, Primary (1988-1994)

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Psychology Professor

JOSE RIZAL UNIVERSITY

Mandaluyong City
January 23, 2023 -
present

Research Consultant / Academic Writer

RACKPAPER ONLINE EDUCATIONAL CONSULTANCY SERVICES

Mandaluyong City
May 2022 - present

Content Writer/Academic Writer

RACKPAPER WRITING SERVICES

2015 - Present

Guidance Counselor / Student Affairs Officer

STI College Shaw

Shaw Boulevard, Pasig City
February 4, 2013 – March 2014

Part time General Subject Instructor

STI College Shaw

Shaw Boulevard, Pasig City
February 4, 2013 – March 2014

FEU Institute of Technology

Psychology Professor

P. Paredes Street, Sampaloc, Manila
November 2012 – February 2013

Associate, Monitoring Technician

Emerson Electric Asia LTD ROHQ

San Miguel Properties Center, Mandaluyong City
May 28, 2012 – November 28, 2012

General Education Professor

(College of Arts and Sciences)

Rizal Technological University, Mandaluyong City
July 10, 2009 – November 2011
November 2016 - 2017

Ethics/IT Professor

(College of Engineering & Industrial Technology)

Rizal Technological University, Mandaluyong City
November 4, 2009 – October 15, 2010

Home Based/Online Private Tutor (Elementary and High School level)

June 2007 – up to present

HR Officer / General Subject Instructor

AMA Computer Learning Center – Mandaluyong/Guadalupe Branch
June 13, 2006 – April 15, 2007

General Subject Instructor

AMA Computer Learning Center – Mandaluyong/Guadalupe Branch
June 13, 2006 – April 15, 2007

Subjects taught: General Psychology, Sociology, Ethics, NSTP

Part Time Researcher (Project based)

New Era University
November 2003 – January 2006

Telemarketer

Yellow Cab Pizza Co.
January 11, 2003 – June 11, 2004

Private Tutor (Elementary and High School level)

June 2002 – March 2006